

CULTURAL CENTERS ARE A PLACE OF KNOWLEDGE AND ENLIGHTENMENT

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Abstract: This article talks about opportunities in cultural centers as an object of talent and ability formation. Also, the attention paid to reading today is compared with foreign countries.

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It is observed that the high level of development, the technological way of life teaches people to move less. For example, "Google Translate", which is a wide picture in modern information systems, is able to translate any text into different foreign languages fast. A person who has adapted to automatic translation does not go deep into the content of the text. It calls the attention of people to the given text with the help of the translation program, i.e. brings it into social and educational consumption. Repeated repetition of this situation leads people to become subject to intelligence in information systems. In short, this approach accelerates the robotization of people, or modern information systems weaken the incentive of people to search for unexpected realities in the fields of science, to create new things, to make discoveries.

In the past, they entered the libraries and looked through the literature recorded in hundreds of catalogs on a certain topic and selected the most suitable one as the object of research. It is worth saying that in libraries, books would be in the hands of readers, and the necessary books would have to be returned. Now, modern information system (internet) is satisfied with information and other literature. It is certainly a pity that the number of visitors to traditional libraries in the world has decreased dramatically. In this regard, the process of global virtualization is taking place. It is necessary to carefully consider these circumstances in labor education.

It is not an exaggeration to say that cultural centers are a place where students can acquire additional knowledge and practical and theoretical skills outside of general education schools. In cultural centers, students or listeners organize their free time meaningfully by participating in various art directions, as well as being members of various courses and clubs.

Older people used to be the favorite places of the village youth - cultural centers - these places were very crowded with young and old people. It's natural to have

a question. Why was the need for cultural centers high now? Today, although this area has been raised to the level of state policy, the population faces problems, especially in attracting young people? The answer is one. When the main function of cultural centers is still not resolved.

The possibilities of attracting any subject to this object have not been thoroughly thought out.

The head of our country Sh.Mirziyoev's discussed the issues of wide involvement of the population, especially the youth, in cultural centers, in the meeting with the intellectuals of our country on August 3, 2017. After this assignment and subsequent decisions, cultural centers have been extensively renovated. We have touched on this in our previous topics.

Of course, the question arises why cultural centers are places of education and enlightenment. The cultural center is like a mirror to the visiting person, where the student realizes his own talent and education, and is considered as a place where he can acquire knowledge and skills. For example, in the cultural centers today there are clubs in various directions of art, courses oriented to certain professions, clubs such as "The fun and The smart" and "Zakovat" for those who are interested.

In order to attract the population to the cultural centers, mobile film studios and film distribution centers are being established. This process consists of meaningful organization of the student's free time after school. In addition, with the initiatives of President Shavkat Mirziyoev, great attention is paid to books and reading. Libraries are being established in neighborhoods. Of course, all this will give its positive results in increasing the culture of reading, expanding the thinking and spiritual world of the young generation. Besides, reading a book is hard work, and the heart attached to it is far from hardships. At this point, our Honorable President said, "Books are a means of changing people's consciousness, worldview, and raising their spiritual level. Development and high spirituality cannot be achieved without books. It is appropriate to remember meaningful opinion that neither a person nor a nation has a future who does not read books.

Today, practical measures, cooperation projects are being implemented by the Ministry of Culture to increase the book fund in cultural centers. Heads of state organizations are participating in actions to donate artistic and scientific books to schools, cultural centers, and libraries in order to enrich book funds.

First of all, high-quality printing of books that meet the spiritual-educational, artistic-aesthetic requirements of young people, supporting the activities of

publishers and creators, supporting the publication of children's literature, translating the best examples of national and world literature, reading urgent tasks such as improving the culture, developing the reading culture in remote areas of the republic and age-related, systematically studying the reading level and interest in books of the population, organizing projects and contests aimed at developing the reading culture.

In addition, in recent years, the work on promotion of reading culture among young people in our country has increased to a qualitative level.

In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 13, 2017 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture", the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 781 of December 14, 2020 with the national program for the development and support of reading culture in 2020-2025 and a number of other documents serve as a program for the development of the sector.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 781 of December 14, 2020, it was planned to implement the national program for the development and support of reading culture in 2020-2025 in three stages.

The first stage of this is the implementation of measures to improve organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of reading culture in 2020-2021;

the second stage - strengthening of reading infrastructure in 2022-2023;

the third stage - in 2024-2025, important criteria such as the rapid development of the reading culture of young people and the improvement of the quality of human capital due to the growth of their intellectual potential have been set.

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Developing a system for evaluating the effectiveness of the measures implemented in the development of reading, introducing ratings such as "The

best reading region", "The best reading neighborhood", "The best reading educational institution" and other important tasks have been defined.

The book has an incomparable educational value in bringing up a spiritually mature generation, educating them in the spirit of patriotism and patriotism. Therefore, it is reading that gives knowledge and information to a person and enriches his spiritual world. A good book helps to find answers to the most difficult questions.

According to "NOP World" international rating agency, people in the world spend 16.6 hours a week watching TV, 8.9 hours in front of the computer, and 6.5 hours for reading. In 2016, in the list of countries with the most books per week, India - 10.7, Thailand - 9.4, China - 8, Philippines - 7.6, Czech Republic - 7.4, Russia - 7.1, Sweden - 6.9, France — 6.9 and Hungary — 6.8 hours.

The fact that publishing activities are developing and book reading is becoming more popular shows that the idea that people will lose interest in reading books as audio, video means of communication, radio, television, and information communication networks occupy a deep place in our lives is a mistake. As each process has its own beneficial and harmful consequences, it is not an exaggeration to say that the development of information and communication and information in digital format has reduced reading in people's lives.

The study of the demand for books in the world by a number of agencies has shown that in the last 30 years, the production of book products of the same name has increased three times, and the number has increased four times. Today, about a million books are published in the world every year. For example, 10 books are printed per person in the USA, 9.5 in Russia, 5 in France, and 3.5 in China.

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